

A STUDY ON QUALITY OF WORK LIFE OF TEACHERS EMPLOYED IN PRIVATE ARTS AND SCIENCE COLLEGES WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO TIRUPUR DISTRICT

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Cite This Article: Dr. B. Thayumanavar & K. Srivignesh Kumar, "A Study on Quality of Work Life of Teachers Employed in Private Arts and Science Colleges With Special Reference to Tirupur District", International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Modern Education, Volume 3, Issue 1, Page Number 130-135, 2017.

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Abstract:

Higher education is the key of success of a nation which boosts the economic potential of entire nation leading to the development of the nation. This is like a middleware transformation engine which produces manpower for industry, develop entrepreneurs and motivates young minds for R&D. This responsibility is on the shoulders of educational employees to understand and transform the energy and knowledge of students in an effective and efficient manner. An abundance of research studies suggested that the quality of work life (QWL) is one of the most significant and efficient tools of human resource management. Quality of work life programs encourage employees, make balance between professional, personal & social life and ultimately enhances employee job satisfaction.

Key Words: Quality & Work-Life and Job Satisfaction

Arts and Science Colleges in Tirupur:

This article fetch out the List of Arts & Science Colleges in Tirupur district. Tirupur has a remarkable place in Tamil Nadu. Tirupur is also referred as a Textile City, Knit City, Dollar City and Kutti Japan (Small Japan) due to the huge amount garments exports around the world. Here is the list provides you about the numbers of Arts and Science Colleges located in and around Tirupur District.

An Overview:

The booming industrial growth and the scramble for employees made offering a good quality of work life and work/life balance strategic for hiring, retention and the bottom line. Then came the millennium and soon after, a recession, corporate scandals and cutbacks. Some feared the QWL approach to employee management would vanish along with dot-coms, IT and ITES organizations that engage the new generation workers who seem never loyal to the employers. However, the idea of a Quality of Work Life has weathered the storms and is alive and well. In fact, QWL programs after millennium year are poised to help HR professionals and other executives face the next wave of personnel challenges. Organizations now have what Human Resource has always had: a heightened awareness of the value of people and all of the related developments in metrics, assessments, benchmarking and performance management. As all the organizations are growing fast and sustaining their growth rates considerably and new opportunities present themselves, organizations will be looking for ways to hold on to those valuable employees. And at present, HR professionals will have their corporate peers on their side in supporting creative steps to keep workers – and keep them happy. QWL programs can be a big player, especially now, when the workers are becoming too loyal to their employment and not to their employers and it may prevent or limit the organization's ability to reward workers in other ways. Companies are also adapting QWL programs to the entrance of generation Y into the workplace. Different in many ways from generation Xers, this new group of workers have their own vision for the workplace and their careers, one that QWL programs can help to fulfill. Hence it is the appropriate time to evaluate the activities related to the QWL programs that organizations are adopting and in what extent they have to look forward to improve the same in the future. The author hopes that the QWL programs/surveys will help to assess the present HR practices and to identify the future directions. The researcher by going through above literature review identified that no study was conducted in the past regarding the QWL of private Arts and Science college teachers in Tirupur District. This industry is having exponential growth and faced numerous problems related to human resource issues concerned with employees (teachers) turnover, frequent horizontal shift of the employees within the units, higher level of stress in their jobs, greater job dissatisfaction, poor work-life balance and poor Quality of Work Life perceived by them, etc. It was therefore the right time to analyze and address above said problems for which a study on Quality of Work Life of the employees was quite appropriate and it might help to

find ways to improve the QWL of employees and to redefining of the guidelines and policies to support QWL in the industry.

Objectives of the Study:

The study approaches the problem from the viewpoint of both the employees and the employers to attain the Quality of Work Life in the private Arts and science colleges in Tirupur District. The main objective of the study is to know how the employees are balancing their work and life by which they attain the Quality of Work Life. The following are the broader objectives of the study:

- ✓ To assess the personal profile of the employees of private Arts and Science colleges in Tirupur District and its influence on the various dimensions of Quality of Work Life.
- ✓ To identify the critical dimensions related to Quality of Work Life.
- ✓ To identify the critical major factors that influences the Quality of Work Life.
- ✓ To assess the Quality of Work Life attained by the employees of private Arts and Science colleges in Tirupur District.
- ✓ To analyze the support rendered by the employers to improve the Quality of Work Life of their employees.
- ✓ To assess the effectiveness of the employees in achieving their Work Life Balance.

Hypotheses:

The following hypotheses have been framed in the light of the above objectives:

- ✓ Employees do not attain their Quality of Work Life significantly.
- ✓ Employees do not achieve their Work Life Balance significantly.
- ✓ The personal profile of the employees and the grouping according to age, gender, income, educational qualification, size of the organization and the nature of the organization does not influence the Quality of Work Life.
- ✓ The factors Job factor, Job culture & climate and Participation in Union do not significantly influence the Perceived Work Quality.
- ✓ The factors Health outcome and Benefits & Work Load do not significantly influence the Perceived Life Quality.
- ✓ There is significant difference between the theorized model and the model arrived at from the research data.

Period of the Study:

Both primary and secondary data were employed in the study. Primary data was collected from the respondents using a questionnaire. Data collection was done during the period of November 2012 to April 2015. For tracing the achievements and developments of the Private Arts and Science Colleges in Tirupur District, secondary data for a period of 10 years was considered.

Limitations of the Study:

The study consumed lot of time and threw up several problems and became a challenge for the researcher to complete the data collection. Considerable time and care had to be bestowed to collect unbiased data. However adequate time and interest could not be realized in the case of many respondents because of lack of interest of their employers. The inferences of the study are thus subject to inherent limitations in both the primary and secondary data. Apart from this, the other limitations are:

- ✓ The results of the study are applicable to Private Arts and Science Colleges in Tirupur District only and are not to be generalized for the entire Education sector.
- ✓ The research constraints of the researcher did not allow him to conduct the research more elaborately with a larger size of sample.
- ✓ Around four hundred Teaching staffs (employees) are directly engaged in the Private Arts and Science Colleges in Tirupur District; only 250 questionnaires were distributed among them and only 246 questionnaires could be collected from the respondents, which are complete in all aspects. The analysis has been done, inferences drawn and interpretation arrived at with these 246 responses only; hence the results are arrived at 95% level of confidence.

Table 1: One way Analysis of Variance among Age of the respondents and perception towards various dimensions of quality of work life

S. No	Source	Df	SS	MS	$\bar{X}$	Statistical Inference
1	Work Environment / Work Flexibility				G1= 56.7969	F=2.057 P>0.05 Not Significant
	Between Groups	3	437.399	145.800	G2= 55.7419	
	Within Groups	246	17440.217	70.895	G3= 53.3286	
					G4= 54.8696	
2	Additional Work Load				G1= 43.9063	F=7.037 P<0.01
	Between Groups	3	2275.912	758.637	G2= 36.9140	

	Within Groups	246	26521.752	107.812	G3=	40.2143	Significant
					G4=	44.3478	
3	Work Culture				G1=	60.1250	F=2.550 P<0.05 Significant
	Between Groups	3	1073.451	357.817	G2=	56.0645	
	Within Groups	246	34522.613	140.336	G3=	57.0000	
					G4=	62.0000	
4	Health Outcomes and Other Outcomes				G1=	55.7344	F=3.671 P<0.05 Significant
	Between Groups	3	1675.462	558.487	G2=	49.7097	
	Within Groups	246	37423.902	152.130	G3=	51.7714	
					G4=	55.7826	
5	Benefits and Compensation				G1=	36.9844	F=6.075 P<0.01 Significant
	Between Groups	3	1797.236	599.079	G2=	34.6667	
	Within Groups	246	24259.820	98.617	G3=	39.6286	
					G4=	43.0870	
6	Overall level of quality of life				G1=	253.5469	F= 5.187 P<0.01 Significant
	Between Groups	3	23012.098	7670.699	G2=	233.0968	
	Within Groups	246	363763.586	1478.714	G3=	241.9429	
					G4=	260.0870	

G1= 25-30 years G2= 31-35 years G3= 36-40 years G4= above 40 years

The Table No 1 evident that there is a significant variance among the age of the respondents and various dimensions of quality of work life such as Additional Work load, Work Culture, Health Outcomes and Other Outcomes, Benefits and Compensation and Overall level of Quality of work life. However there is no significant variance among the age of the respondents and dimension of quality of work life of Work Environment / Work Flexibility. The mean score indicates that who belongs to age group of above 40 years have had higher level of favourable perception towards overall level of quality of work life. The age has influence the level of perception towards quality of work life.

Table 2: One way Analysis of Variance among Monthly Income of the respondents and perception towards various dimensions of quality of work life

S. No	Source	Df	SS	MS	$\bar{X}$		Statistical Inference
1	Work Environment / Work Flexibility				G1=	56.3607	F=3.011 P<0.05 Significant
	Between Groups	4	837.565	209.391	G2=	56.9367	
	Within Groups	246	17040.051	69.551	G3=	52.3617	
					G4=	53.6600	
					G5=	56.4615	
2	Additional Work Load				G1=	38.6066	F=4.194 P<0.01 Significant
	Between Groups	4	1845.458	461.365	G2=	40.9873	
	Within Groups	246	26952.206	110.009	G3=	41.7234	
					G4=	42.5800	
					G5=	30.3846	
3	Work Culture				G1=	56.2295	F=2.397 P<0.05 Significant
	Between Groups	4	1340.356	335.089	G2=	57.7975	
	Within Groups	246	34255.708	139.819	G3=	55.4255	
					G4=	61.9800	
					G5=	59.8462	
4	Health Outcomes and Other Outcomes				G1=	52.7541	F=2.575 P<0.01 Significant
	Between Groups	4	1577.438	394.360	G2=	52.3924	
	Within Groups	246	37521.926	153.151	G3=	49.1064	
					G4=	56.2800	
					G5=	47.5385	
5	Benefits and Compensation				G1=	39.1803	F=4.074 P<0.01

	Between Groups	4	1625.255	406.314	G2=	35.3038	Significant
	Within Groups	246	24431.801	99.722	G3=	36.5957	
					G4=	40.9200	
					G5=	31.6154	
6	Overall level of quality of life				G1=	243.1311	F= 2.365 P<0.05 Significant
	Between Groups	4	14381.773	3595.443	G2=	243.4177	
	Within Groups	246	372393.911	1519.975	G3=	235.2128	
					G4=	255.4200	
					G5=	225.8462	

G1= Below Rs. 10000 G2= Rs. 10001-15000 G3= Rs. 15001-20000

G4= Rs. 20001-25000 G5= Above Rs. 25000

The Table No 2 evident that there is a significant variance among the monthly income of the respondents and various dimensions of quality of work life such as Work Environment / Work Flexibility, Additional Work load, Work Culture, Health Outcomes and Other Outcomes, Benefits and Compensation and Overall level of Quality of work life. The mean score indicates that who belongs to monthly income group of above Rs. 25,000 have had higher level of favourable perception towards overall level of quality of work life. The monthly income has influence the level of perception towards quality of work life.

Table 3: One way Analysis of Variance among opinion on reasons for selection this profession of the respondents and perception towards various dimensions of quality of work life

S. No	Source	Df	SS	MS	$\bar{X}$		Statistical Inference
1	Work Environment / Work Flexibility				G1=	55.1547	F=7.691 P<0.01 Significant
	Between Groups	4	1994.413	498.603	G2=	63.2222	
	Within Groups	246	15883.203	64.829	G3=	48.5294	
					G4=	55.5128	
					G5=	68.0000	
2	Additional Work Load				G1=	40.0773	F=9.352 P<0.01 Significant
	Between Groups	4	3814.510	953.627	G2=	48.5556	
	Within Groups	246	24983.154	101.972	G3=	37.5882	
					G4=	37.9487	
					G5=	67.0000	
3	Work Culture				G1=	57.8066	F=3.491 P<0.01 Significant
	Between Groups	4	1919.477	479.869	G2=	67.4444	
	Within Groups	245	33676.587	137.455	G3=	60.4706	
					G4=	54.0513	
					G5=	68.0000	
4	Health Outcomes and Other Outcomes				G1=	52.0829	F=3.234 P<0.05 Significant
	Between Groups	4	1961.013	490.253	G2=	59.3333	
	Within Groups	246	37138.351	151.585	G3=	50.4706	
					G4=	51.1282	
					G5=	71.0000	
5	Benefits and Compensation				G1=	36.0663	F=3.145 P<0.05 Significant
	Between Groups	4	1272.533	318.133	G2=	41.0000	
	Within Groups	246	24784.523	101.161	G3=	39.3529	
					G4=	41.5897	
					G5=	42.0000	
6	Overall level of quality of life				G1=	241.1878	F= 6.085 P<0.01 Significant
	Between Groups	4	34952.808	8738.202	G2=	279.5556	
	Within Groups	246	351822.876	1436.012	G3=	236.4118	
					G4=	240.2308	
					G5=	316.0000	

G1= Respectable Profession G2= Status symbol G3= Realistic Working hours

G4= Teachers Motivation G5= Family Members as role Models

The Table No.3 evident that there is a significant variance among the reasons for selection this profession of the respondents and various dimensions of quality of work life such as Work Environment / Work Flexibility, Additional Work load, Work Culture, Health Outcomes and Other Outcomes, Benefits and Compensation and Overall level of Quality of work life. The mean score indicates that opined that Family Members as role Models for selection this profession have had higher level of favourable perception towards overall level of quality of work life. The reasons for selection this profession has influence the level of perception towards quality of work life.

Table 4: One way Analysis of Variance among Earning members in their family of the respondents and perception towards various dimensions of quality of work life

S. No	Source	Df	SS	MS	$\bar{X}$		Statistical Inference
1	Work Environment / Work Flexibility				G1=	51.5185	F=3.018 P<0.05 Significant
	Between Groups	3	634.707	211.569	G2=	55.3469	
	Within Groups	246	17242.909	70.093	G3=	58.3600	
					G4=	58.0000	
2	Additional Work Load				G1=	41.0741	F=2.728 P<0.05 Significant
	Between Groups	3	927.180	309.060	G2=	39.5255	
	Within Groups	246	27870.484	113.295	G3=	44.6400	
					G4=	53.0000	
3	Work Culture				G1=	62.0000	F=1.961 P>0.05 Not Significant
	Between Groups	3	831.208	277.069	G2=	56.9694	
	Within Groups	246	34764.856	141.321	G3=	60.7200	
					G4=	60.0000	
4	Health Outcomes and Other Outcomes				G1=	53.9630	F=0.247 P>0.05 Not Significant
	Between Groups	3	117.259	39.086	G2=	52.1735	
	Within Groups	246	38982.105	158.464	G3=	52.7200	
					G4=	48.0000	
5	Benefits and Compensation				G1=	39.2963	F=0.616 P>0.05 Not Significant
	Between Groups	3	194.134	64.711	G2=	37.4235	
	Within Groups	246	25862.922	105.134	G3=	35.6800	
					G4=	34.0000	
6	Overall level of quality of life				G1=	247.8519	F=0.721 P>0.05 Not Significant
	Between Groups	3	3371.371	1123.790	G2=	241.4388	
	Within Groups	246	383404.313	1558.554	G3=	252.1200	
					G4=	253.0000	

G1= one member G2= Two members G3= Three members G4= Four members

The Table No 4 evident that there is a significant variance among the earning members in the family of the respondents and various dimensions of quality of work life such as Work Environment / Work Flexibility and Additional Work load. However there is no significant variance among the earning members in the family of the respondents and various dimensions of quality of work life such as Work Culture, Health Outcomes and Other Outcomes, Benefits and Compensation and Overall level of Quality of work life. The earning members in the family has not influence the level of perception towards quality of work life.

Conclusion:

The age group of above 40 years have had higher level of favourable perception towards overall level of quality of work life. The age has influence the level of perception towards quality of work life. The monthly income has influence the level of perception towards quality of work life. This profession have had higher level of favourable perception towards overall level of quality of work life. The reasons for selection this profession has influence the level of perception towards quality of work life. The earning members in the family has not influence the level of perception towards quality of work life. In this scenario, high quality of work life is essential for organizations to continue to attract and retain employees. This is the reason QWL concept has gained momentum recently and researches are going on worldwide to find out inputs for framing effective QWL strategies. Moreover the literature review discussed above also supports the relationship between QWL, employee performance and career growth aspects. Still many facets of QWL need to be unexplored through further studies.

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